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The Pedagogy School Occupation

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Abstract

The school occupation, a practice which occurs in educational activities formal and non-formal, evidenced historically by the fight for school by working classes, with notoriety in the MST action - Landless Workers' Movement – and also from student movement, and, in the recent events of public school students, taking his school space, it appears as a category of analysis of the educational field in its entirety. So the political, collective, socio-cultural and educational school occupation will be exposed. It is noted that the school occupation contains elements that support them as pedagogy, a category of analysis of educational practice, both as a social movement, as, in potential terms, the Brazilian public school system.

Keywords: School Occupation, Integral human formation, Politics, Collectivity and Self-Management

Introduction

The Brazilian educational reality, more intensely in recent years, has coexisted with the practice of occupying schools by students, especially High School students. This article intends to highlight the pedagogical character of these occupations, however, it is necessary to say, initially, that the occupation of schools is not a contemporary phenomenon, it is a practice already carried out in other times and spaces, and the pedagogical character to be outlined is made in the category of school occupation in a broad manner.

Considering the historical conditions of production, the designation of occupation has come to mean as a political and social practice from the MST (their preferred abbreviation) – Landless Rural Worker Movement, which uses occupation as a political strategy to cause tension to the state for the fulfillment of the agrarian reform – such reform that aims to occupy the space categorized as unproductive to make it immediately productive and, thus, capable of considering it as land for an agrarian reform. In addition to unproductive lands, the MST also occupies symbolic places for the struggle for land. Thus, in this present exhibition, the most striking material basis for indication and analysis is hereinafter titled pedagogy of school occupation. It has direct contribution of this social movement and its educational practices (all practices of struggle taken as educational) and school practices. The study is documentary, analytical, and quantitative based on bibliographic resources, but effectively linked to empirical research. Therefore, from the first considerations, this text desires to establish a theoretical-practical relationship, involving aspects of the real, of school observations and of broad perspectives contained in the social understanding of the occupation category.

It highlights then, elements that are present in occupations, since their historical constitution and considering different practices, in different spaces, for both the point of convergence is the school: either in the search of subjects for school, or in the internal dispute in the conduction of educational processes within the state systems that organize the school space and school units. That is, still, in processes of resistance of

students, with their demands, that do not abandon the centrality of school life.

In its methodological format, this article stems from a model originated at a doctoral thesis in education, (Martins, 2011), which, when studying school occupation, establishes the dimensions that constitute themselves as categories in the educational debate and that we will discuss later. To update and validate the model displayed, it also carries out a screening and analysis of data on a Brazilian scientific base, the portal of journals Capes, which significantly concentrates scientific production and, therefore, is representative for investigations of such nature.

In this way, a corpus for analysis was established about the occupation of schools, and its content was analyzed (the description of the data processing is found in the discussion of the article) and applied to the aforementioned model, to support what is called pedagogy of school occupation. Thus, the qualitative character lies only in the delimitation of the set of information from research carried out on the theme. The research data, the model adopted, and the results of this research are anchored in the qualitative and dialectical analysis of the theme.

Theory and literature review

Occupation is, in general, a tool for the struggle of various social movements. It gains strength and systematization under the aegis of the Marxist paradigm of social movements (Gohn, 2014) as pointed out in the entry “occupation of places” in the French Dictionary of social movements (Penissat, 2020). The concept has been expanded and receiving other applications, as evidenced by this same dictionary, which in a new edition introduces the entry “occupation of squares” (Nez, 2020). Thus, we see spaces that are claimed by a portion of society being occupied: streets, squares, public and private buildings. The verb occupy positions itself in the field of resistance, demand for rights, visibility. It is with this greater scope that we approach the theme to be developed in this article, when defining a pedagogy for the occupation of schools, we apply the tool of social organization to a specific place, to practice, more precisely to schools.

The empirical field of the model adopted here and of the constant practices in all the productions that make up the bibliographic research is Brazil, and in this space, it is necessary to highlight some characteristics in the delimitation of the occupation to the school reality, thus, two pieces of information are necessary about movements of Brazilian society. First, a social movement of national and international relevance - the Landless Rural Workers Movement – MST, in its educational practice and schools, provided a collaboration for the concept of school occupation, including the analytical model used in this article, comes from studies on the MST. Secondly: the movement of school occupation by students - other than the ones from MST - aiming at obtaining demands specific to the school reality. This phenomenon is not restricted only to Brazil, has Latin American roots (Martins, 2022), but the massification of this practice in national demonstrations in the years 2015 and 2016 in Brazilian territory, left a significant analytical contribution, which makes up a relevant part of the scientific production analyzed in the article.

Nevertheless, while the model used has empirical bases in MST schools, it can be highlighted that it is also made up of analyses that go beyond this particular movement, based on other experiences of occupation of schools in the Brazilian context and composed of support categories that extrapolate, including, occupation practices.

In a synthetic and schematic way, this article aims to build the foundation for a pedagogy of the occupation of schools, from the following model, already referenced in the introduction of the paper, and visually exposed:

The figure also indicates as the basis of the dimensions of the occupation of the school a series of categories enshrined in the educational debate. For the purpose of theoretical localization, it is worth noting that labor is foundational for the marxist understanding of education, also explained by Gramsci (2017), or even by the theorists of the Russian school, such as Pistrak, Makarenko and their contemporaries. In this perspective, labor is seen as an educational principle, and begins to constitute itself as a pedagogical instrument.

As a form of complementation and application of the category labor, one can mention a triad of Marxian thought (put here) with the sum of two other basal categories: praxis and emancipation, which in the set of reflections here, can figure as method and objective. Praxis as a method even has the function of materializing labor as an educational principle, making it not only reside in a theoretical conception about educational practice, but reach the pedagogical daily life. In the understanding exposed by Vázquez (2011), praxis is a category that inextricably articulates the aspects of theory and an effective practical applicability, although it aims at transformation, the present author evidences that practice as the face of the process, it can materialize in actualization actions (of?), as are the school educational procedures. Such combined actions are aimed at the emancipation of the individual who is educated in this process. The category of emancipation, although very present in the educational debate, is plural. It is known that the Marxian tradition supports it, however, significant interpretations have constituted the debate, as does the Frankfurt School with its representatives Theodor Adorno and J. D. H. Habermas, which in fact composes the understanding of the category. However, in this text, as an alignment with the categories previously exposed, we use the Marxian understanding (Marx, 2010) about emancipation, which is concerned with the emancipation of subjects in their various possibilities (religious, political, human) and has as its unequivocal purpose the social dimension of emancipation, with which we share.

In addition to the category of emancipation, in a more subjective context, there is the category autonomy, essential for the teaching-learning process. Already detached from the purely philosophical conceptualization, the autonomy applied to education, outlined by Paulo Freire (2019) focused on educational practice, in a learning project in which students are protagonists in the process. As a result, they are instrumented with knowledge that guarantees their decision and action power, mediated by the knowledge acquired in the teaching and learning process.

The previously cited categories are fully viable in another category, of collectivity, which reaches the substantiated proposals in this paper. Makarenko (2012), anchored in concrete experiences, albeit in a diverse educational context, focuses its efforts on educational “communes”, evidencing that collectivity is more than the sum of individuals, but a living organism that undertakes significant educational changes. Which it implies the set of categories adopted as the theoretical reference of this article but is also visible in the practice of the occupation process of schools studied in this investigation.

The totality of the categories displayed, according to the model taken as reference for this article, support the dimensions of school occupation, and, in the understanding here defended, also the professed “pedagogy” contained in the actions that culminate in the occupation. By expanding the range of interlocutions, with the state-of-the-art on the subject, it is also possible to affirm that the categories exhibited are also present in all the investigated works, even if they are not taken as central, they are present both in the analyzes and in the investigated practices. To better visualize the statements, we proceed to the demonstration and methodological design of the data obtained.

Methodology – Corpus of referential production

Addressing the need to confront the proposed model with a more up-to-date and comprehensive reality, we conducted a bibliographic research, with bibliometric and exploratory elements in the CAPES (Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel) journal portal, foundation of the Ministry of Education of Brazil, which had been launched in the year 2000. This database has served as a reference for academic research for more than a decade, reviews of its academic use were already published (Cendon and Ribeiro, 2008) indicating its potential, and even today, it is a reference for research, to assess new themes in academic debates (Zanotti and Carvalho, 2021).

Methodologically, a literature search was carried out on the theme with the following descriptors: occupation and school. The search was exact and restricted to titles of works, since the expansion of such scope resulted in millions of titles. Thus, such delimitation was significant and consistent. No temporal restrictions were imposed, accepting works of different years of elaboration, resulting in texts written between 2009 and 2021. This search has February 26, 2022 as the reference date of data collection. With the indicators mentioned, 52 results were obtained, treated and systematized, two studies were excluded that referred to architecture issues, about constructions and evaluations, of this area of knowledge and another with debates about the occupation, from the perspective of occupational therapy, both outside the scope of the research proposed here. Which determined the effective number of texts to be analyzed as 49 (forty-nine) articles of peer-reviewed scientific journals, two texts with their own characteristics: one in the form of an interview and the other in the format of an editorial. Apart from one Spanish journal, all the others are Brazilian journals.

The journals' scopes are found in their profile, and accordingly, the areas of knowledge in which they are inserted. The present sample had small adjustments in two situations: first, the insertion of a journal defined as humanities in the interdisciplinary area, and; second, the relocation, in view of the tradition of publication, of the debates regarding the “world of labor” to the area of education. After these adjustments, they were systematized in the following numbers:

The table clearly indicates, although the predominance is in the area of education with twenty-five articles, a multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary approach to the phenomenon of school occupation. An emphasis on communication tools used in occupation processes, mainly by High School students in the movements of occupying their schools exposes the second highest concentration in the focus area of communication with eight papers published. The legal questions and clashes in the judiciary power about the legality of the act of occupying constitutes the third largest approach in the area of law, with five studies. The areas that complete the survey follow the trend of interdisciplinary approaches (area with three works) and multidisciplinary, counting on three works in history, two in social sciences and geography, and more particular areas, such as physical education with an investigation evidencing the scope of the phenomenon studied.

We also systematized the methodological format that the studies were carried out. Before any exhibition of data it is necessary to emphasize that, in the social sciences in general, with greater emphasis on the theme delimitation chosen here, the reference to “theoretical” studies has its distinct particularities compared to the field of STEM, for example. The theory referred to is always the systematization of practices, it involves field research, empirical experiences. That is, the theoretical works that deal with only the methodological format of access to information, which in its entirety are derived from concrete realities, experiences contained in other systematizations already carried out, such as, for example, reviews of studies already published, or systematizations in judicial processes and their records. And given the specific systematization of the area, we excluded from the “theoretical” field the methodologies concentrated in the social communication media, both in communication and application networks, as well as analysis of productions.

After this consideration, there is a large block of sixteen (16) works grouped around the methodology using theoretical studies and the other thirty-three (33) distributed in other methodological formats. For exhibition purposes, we grouped approximate methodologies, which does not intend to affirm that they are the same methodological formats, since each research brings its uniqueness and approach. For the demonstration in this article, the methodologies were: interviews, DICT (digital information and communication technologies), workshops, focus group and discussion group, image analysis, documentary, and film, participant research, case study, oral history and ethnography.

It is also necessary to emphasize that there are works that combine more than one type of methodological strategy in their investigation process. As an example, most of the activities, even those cataloged as theoretical, were part of a participatory research process. However, methodologies described as such specifically are expressed within the studies themselves and were framed in the present distribution.

In general, it is necessary to emphasize that the methodologies pointed out and systematized, seek, in their vast majority, to provide the voice to the subjects of movements within the category of occupation, independently of any space that it happens. Also, it is necessary to emphasize again that segmented exposure is merely illustrative, since studies, on several occasions, combine strategies to highlight their results.

Looking at the set of bibliographic productions, it can be seen that there is an evident emphasis on the movements promoted by Brazilian high school students in two waves: a movement whose epicenter was the state of São Paulo in 2015, but with actions also in other Brazilian states, and a second wave, of a national character, with the same format, occurred in 2016, with a greater concentration in the state of Paraná (Medeiros, Januario and Melo, 2019). In the analysis of the forty-nine articles with the descriptors occupation and school, forty of them focus on this phenomenon. Thus, of the remaining approaches, we have a very heterogeneous set that is worth of a more accurate cataloging. For better use of the visual resources in the tables, we will systematize only the concentration of items that go beyond the occupation movement of Brazilian schools by students in the years 2015 and 2016, focusing on the remaining nine studies. Although the approaches are quite different, it is possible to make some groupings in such investigations, as I explain in the following demonstration:

As this is a small number of studies, different from other points of quantitative demonstration of the studies

analyzed in this article, it is possible to make a more precise identification of the analyzed corpus. Referencing what was said in the introduction of the paper, in Brazil, the Landless Rural Workers Movement - MST has a prominent place in front of the occupation category, and concentrates more work about their daily lives, in schools, and also relating to the category proposed here. Around the concept of identity, distinct debates are grouped: the space of indigenous schools and its relations with the community, the place of language in strengthening national identities and debates of alterity related to students with intellectual disabilities. We denominate with the expression public versus private a text that deals with the question of the occupation via private market logic within the public school, via school curriculum. Finally, the housing theme is the most self-explanatory of this set of works, which extrapolate the movements of student occupations.

The themes were grouped around their organizational phenomena, but to other formats of organization, including the content. To finalize this topic of demonstration of the sample used in the article, a brief grouping will be carried out, initially, of a quantitative nature, of the production sample with the analysis model adopted. In other words, an alignment of the number of works with the dimensions of the school occupation category, whose analysis will be carried out later.

In the set of quantitative remarks, the present division of the studies and their approximation with the dimensions of the occupation of the schools is revealed to be the most equitable. What can be attributed to the fluid boundaries between such dimensions, which have complementarities with each other. There is a preponderance in the political dimension, because there are structural approach studies and also general or theoretical analyses on the phenomenon of school occupation, as well as debates from the area of law, which present significant concentration according to the previous graphs. In the sociocultural dimension, studies focus on the identities, constituents or constitutors of the subjects involved in the occupation process, which finds in youth a crucial concept. The collective dimension addresses actions built collectively within the occupation processes of schools. And finally, we denominate the pedagogical dimension the themes that develop direct analyses on learning processes. It is worth noting that this is only a thematic grouping, the analyzes of such studies will take place in the later topic.

Discussion - The pedagogy of school occupation and its dimensions

The set of dimensions systematized here, with regard to the occupation category of the school, maintains a segmentation that is illustrative and didactic, since in the realization of the occupation of the school, the dimensions are integrated in movement. In the construction of a pedagogy, the need for dimensions in their

particularity becomes clearer, since, although they maintain integration in the educational process, they are essential spheres in the process of human development integrally. Thus, the overcoming of the original stage of the applied analytical model (Martins, 2012), which was limited to the definition of a category is found in the evidence of the theoretical-practical considerations of the process, constituting itself as formative, that is, a pedagogy. In the exhibition of the dimensions contained in the adopted model, we will attempt to insert the data obtained through the bibliographic production research according to the premises of the adopted model, resulting in a debate that defines the elements of the pedagogy of school occupation.

1. Political Dimension

Although there are those who defend education as a “neutral” process, the political dimension makes explicit the assumption that education is a political act, as stated in the emancipatory educational debate, which can be synthesized by Paulo Freire. This clash, regarding the educational process of school occupations, the bibliographic research brings a study that materializes the conflict between movements (Carvalho, Feldens, 2021) and points out the position of neutrality around the movement of “school without parties” opposed to the movement of occupation of schools, evidencing, ultimately, the political character immanent to educational practice. The breadth of this debate also reflects the scope of the political dimension, the occupation of schools, and with comprehensive aspects, ranging from the theoretical and ideological clash to the actions of students in the pedagogical daily life and their implications in political personal development.

MST in its practice, confirmed by the studies that deal with the occupation in such a movement, evidence (Martins, 2017, for example) that the search for access to education, in this case, in locations generally forgotten by the state organization, is a fundamental characteristic for an emancipatory pedagogy. In unequal realities, such as the Brazilian one, but which is repeated in numerous peripheral countries, the guarantee of access, or direct access to education is a fundamental condition, which is not fully guaranteed. Thus, there are cases that occupying schools means taking the right to education to certain subjects alienated from all educational systems. Casually, by a semantic approximation (Cafrune, 2014) indicates a crucial element, occupation is also an instrument present in the search for other social and citizenship rights: the right to housing, but also the rights to work, of transportation, food security and others, which are not systematized here due to the scope proposed in the paper.

A highlight in the screening was the significant number of articles in the area of Law (third concentration according to the first table). We relate these debates to the political dimension, understanding that, even mediated by the judiciary, it is a political action in pursuit of the right to education. In their content, the debates focus precisely on an expanded understanding of the right to education, evidencing cases that are taken into account by the legal system the dimensions of collective organization, manifestation (Tavolari, et al. 2018), social control and other dimensions inserted in the concept of possession (Coutinho, 2019).

The right to access to education, in a de facto emancipatory project, needs to be accompanied by the right to remain and to complete one’s studies. It is precisely in this aspect that lies another characteristic of the political dimension of the occupation of schools: the political dispute of the school “content”, elements of the school curriculum, which are disputed in several aspects, including the struggle for the reproduction of the current hegemonic system, as stated in their notes Thiesen and Durli (2016) about the occupation of the private logic of the market in the daily life of public schools. Thus, the school occupation processes also occur in the field of explicit or hidden curriculum of schools, in the search for centrality of students, who are subjects of learning and teaching processes, and often excluded in pedagogical processes. In the insertion of popular, traditional and ancestral knowledge in school dialogues, the occupation of pedagogical processes in the dispute for their objectives and intentionalities, provides greater integration between content and form in pedagogical processes, effecting greater educational potential, to the extent that teaching becomes significant and an integral part of the subjects who are educated.

One of the elements that configure this political occupation of content is precisely the political personal development allied to the acquisition of scientific knowledge. The school occupation movement was very emblematic in this regard. The analyzed works manifest such premises: first the political debate that derives from the processes of occupation, such as the dialogue with intellectuals and their categories (Flach and

Schlesener, 2017); and the systematizations about what political characteristics the students manifest within the processes of occupation, in communication (Altheman, Marques and Martino. 2017), in the use of technologies (Romancini and Castilho, 2017), in the processes of political socialization (Severo and Segundo, 2019), to further analyses that take the phenomenon of occupation as a political action. This set of approaches consolidates a political formative process that is present in the dimension addressed. The set of accumulated and systematized scientific knowledge whose function of schools is to transmit is insufficient. For an integral formation of students, values, citizenship, transformative action are elements from this process of political formation, a fundamental condition for the pedagogy of school occupation.

2. Sociocultural Dimension

The strengthening of learning relations goes through the processes of signification, although subjective, but considerably collective, of the subjects who are involved in the teaching-learning process. In this way, occupying schools is establishing a dialectical relationship of the sociocultural characteristics of the subjects with the formative process. That is, schools need to welcome sociocultural hallmarks, knowledge, collective identities, and in this movement, also reinforce the construction of such identities, when they collaborate for a process of emancipation. Within social movements, the collective identity is formed from the demands pleaded, they also become part of the collective process. As Caldart (2000) has already systematized, when explaining *The Pedagogy of the Landless Movement*, the process of struggle, which, to a certain extent, is valued in the formal educational process, constitutes and reinforces the Landless identity, for example, in this process, school subjects and contents passed over by official curricula, such as the question of agrarian reform. In addition to praxis within social movements, the other manifestations of school occupation found in this study, show the potential of the sociocultural dimension, in which collective identity debates are inserted, as evidenced in the sequence.

The identity mark within social movements, that is, in directed collective processes, is sometimes immanent the culture itself and the constitution of collectives, or even regions, whose tendency is to move away from the school formative process, but they are crucial for the human development of the subjects involved. In one of the analyzed studies there is the significant experience of one of the originary peoples (commonly called indigenous) in southern Brazil, its relationship with the formal school and the centrality of sociocultural development for such segment (Shaan, 2017). Reality that is repeated in several contexts whose school communities have the same characteristics. On another scale, this process can be mentioned as an act of resistance to colonization, either broadly, with the adoption of what is termed as decolonial pedagogy, or in the process of deconstruction within the practices of students' occupations, as evidenced by the research of Corsino and Zan (2017). It is necessary to highlight that the screening of studies with the nomenclature occupation of the school also brought a phenomenon that indicates the use of language as a defense of the national territory in invasion processes by other nations, as evidenced by Ferreira (2021) when narrating East Timor's resistance to Indonesian domination in a Timorese school.

There is a significant diversity in the social fabric of subjects, which reinforce the need for the sociocultural dimension of school occupations. Among the studies analyzed, two aspects stand out in school occupation processes: people with disabilities, (Souza, 2018) and several studies whose focus lies on gender debates, which gained intense visibility during the occupations of Brazilian schools. Students engaged in occupations highlight the need for equality in the distribution of tasks within occupations, demystifying domestic work as essentially female. The debate also boosts and visibility to debates about sexual orientation, by highlighting the presence of the LGBTQIA+ community, as well as the demand for respect about such community, which is commonly discriminated against, with increased emphasis in the present day. It is noteworthy that when dealing with the occupation of schools, it also produces formal learning processes, in the case mentioned, the need for schools to assume and reinforce as a content, the issue of sex education, as school content.

Regarding learning, the traditional posture that remains hegemonic in school institutions, occupations question them in an emblematic way, because, why the culture of youth is not present in school dynamics? The experience of self-management accomplished by the students in the processes of occupation of the schools made in their practices such examination of questions. Among the studies analyzed are researches on

these issues, which highlight the need for schools to insert in its daily life elements proper to informational generations, especially with the insertion of new technologies in learning processes. Languages, artistic manifestations, even the modified profile of the subjects, constitute an educational potential that should not be overlooked by educational institutions. And, on the other hand, self-organized youth highlights the need to be an effective part of the formative process.

3. Collective Dimension

For the development of this dimension of school occupation, a contraposition strategy will be used, evidencing the individualistic character of the self-development process of schools. By making such a contrast, it is also possible to reaffirm the need for the occupation process and the meanings that such a word assumes. There is a social and ideological clash, because many legitimate processes of occupation, as they are highlighted in the studies of the area of law on the subject, to be disqualified, are called "Invasion". Well, we understand that invasions occurs precisely within the capitalist logic in schools, effectively by the adoption of individualistic processes in all of the pedagogical daily life and in the organization of school labor. Didactic processes, evaluation systems, hierarchical and centralized management processes, absence of student participation in all school processes. The logic of competitors and competitions imposed on the school by the capitalist social organization is the real invasion, as other research in the area confirms (Silva, 2022), since, in an objective way, the school institution should be, by its plural constitution, collective.

Contrary to the imposed logic of the capitalist school, the emancipatory formative processes do not renounce collectivity. It is necessary to emphasize that the collective dimension of school occupation exceeds the aggregation of individuals. The collective is a "living organism" (Makarenko, 2012) that is constituted in motion, but, above all, it is also an educator of values, identities and praxis, which go beyond the acquisition of formal cognitive abilities. It is a methodological strategy and also an objective within the teaching-learning process. However, it does not boil down to it, it also covers the processes of school organization and management. Synthetically: a means and a purpose in every formative process.

The designation "invasion" is assigned to the entry into a private property, separate, unconnected to the subjects entering a certain place. When countering this logic, the subjects that occupy ask: if, legally, the land in Brazil needs to have social use, whose land is it? The Landless ask; in cases of abandoned real estate, faced with the constitutional right to housing, whose house, building, apartment, the homeless ask? And, in the most emblematic case, in the occupations of schools by students, subjects of the educational process, whose school is it? To which they respond: "The school is ours" as shown by the study by Kuboyama and Cunha (2019), when analyzing the process of occupation of schools in a city in the interior of Paraná. Thus, the collective dimension of school occupation collaborates with a direct identification, a sense of belonging of the subjects to the school apparatus. This identification contributes directly and indirectly in the teaching-learning process. The experiences analyzed show that the students who occupied the schools, effectively began to understand such institutions as public apparatus, directly related even, with their own subjectivities.

Such belonging materializes in processes of participation. By effectively being part of the school organization process, students and the entire school community engage and build procedures that culminate in learning processes. This includes the environment of the school as well, as was highlighted in the studies researched, in several instances, from providing the right to education in communities that do not have the school apparatus to participate in pedagogical activities, as was quite evidenced in the processes of occupation of schools by Brazilian students. (Rodrigues, Ribeiro, 2017). By exercising the collective dimension of the school, the subjects who are not directly linked to the school dynamics appropriate such a public space, this can be seen in the struggles to build schools in territories not served by formal education. In defense movements against the suppression of school units, especially in rural communities and, the external community, such as the artistic class, civil society organizations, acted effectively in support of the students who occupied the Brazilian schools in their movement.

By dialoguing with the traditional assumptions of the school, the collective dimension can strengthen two devices: democratic management, provided for even legally in Brazilian legislation; and self-management, which can be considered an expansion of the praxis of democratic management. The democratization of management relations is expanded by the participation of the community, of the various subjects that are

around the schools, including social movements. However, within the school occupation movement, students began to understand management elements and interrogate the established practices and even the educational policies imposed on schools (Almeida, Nojiri, 2017). The response to this situation within the occupations was through student self-management, which occurred on several fronts: from the confrontation with restrictive educational policies to the school organization in their daily lives, and, as in the exercise of organization and preservation of pedagogical work, from the maintenance activities (cleaning, food, security) to the main activities, with the structuring of training processes. All these processes observed the collective construction, led by the students as protagonists.

4. Pedagogical Dimension

It is necessary to emphasize that the pedagogical dimension of the occupation of the school, although exhibited in a different way, in practice is precisely the synthesis of the other dimensions, since we understand that, the process of school occupations, is an educational process, in a word: a pedagogy. The previously highlighted dimensions hold pedagogical elements, in this text they will be related to the characteristics directly focused on the teaching and learning process, incorporating previously highlighted elements, and thus, to some extent, amenable to re-presentation of previously mentioned characteristics.

From the outset, we have established a dialogue with the collective dimension regarding management processes and democratic practices. Within the occupation process, the exercise of democracy, participation, self-management generate learning, as was observed on school occupations research (Oliveira, Lousada, Santos, 2020). The involvement, although subjective and individual, in decision-making processes, sharing of responsibilities, direct actions to exercise power, when experienced by students, provide opportunities for learning that enhances the exercise of social democracy, which is so necessary for the exercise of citizenship.

The core of the pedagogical dimension of school occupations is the act of also occupying school contents through the curriculum to be applied in school units. We have already highlighted this need when explaining the sociocultural dimension of the occupation of the school, however, the research done during the occupation processes by the students, evidenced the dialogue directly carried out with the systematically accumulated knowledge, in the election of school contents, directly in the curricular understanding, as demonstrated in the research of Segundo and Severo (2019), whose title evidences the approach that we highlight: "Rethinking the curriculum from the occupation of schools. This rethinking concerns both the general organization of contents, as well as the insertion of significant elements for youth, commonly absent in school realities, even the format that the contents are structured in existing subjects, as indicated by a study (Silva, 2017) focused on educational geography.

In this sense, the pedagogical dimension does not aim to do without science and historically accumulated knowledge. The redesign that was mentioned, gives the centrality and pedagogical attributions to the students, which, traditionally, are only the object of educational policies, curricula and pedagogical processes. To occupy the school "content" is, initially, to insert students in the processes of selection, planning and evaluation of elements that constitute the pedagogical daily life of these same students. And from a scientific material base – which is objective – to establish connections, materialities with language, the methodology that is characteristic of youth and its reality. In a school marked by external centrality and autocratic processes, making students subjects participants in the processes of organizing pedagogical work is essential.

We make harsh criticisms within the article to the organization of the capitalist model of schools, that is, in the prevailing hegemonic model of school. Thus, we cannot conclude the considerations, even more in their pedagogical dimension, without effecting a teleological consideration about the school objectives. A pedagogy of the school occupation, is not restricted to training for higher education levels, for the labor market or pragmatic goals, but rather, it turns to an integral human development, with a view to human and social emancipation. This format was exercised during the process of occupation of schools by students in Brazil, as described by Boutin and Flach (2017). It is salutary to highlight that the occupation processes show the concern in the omnilateral development of students, inserting in the daily school life the issues of self-management of the process, thus exercising the educational character of the collective work; the political development focused on the present time of the country, with the debates about the planning of public policies that affect the population; the care towards issues of identity and also the artistic development, thereby without losing the

focus of maintaining the learning of historically accumulated knowledge.

As a synthesis dimension, the pedagogical dimension contains learning actions in which students are subjects. This is an integral learning, which reaches all the formative dimensions, and interacts with social development, because the objective of occupying the school is to produce a social space with better possibilities of life for all.

Conclusion and closing words

This article combined methodological strategies to highlight the presence of a Pedagogy of School Occupation. Conceptualizations were made about the occupation of schools, narratives of practical elements, evidenced the categories that support the statements. The presentation is based on a literature review research on the topic, which evidences the phenomenon through several searches, and allows quantitatively to observe the presence of the elements highlighted in other studies. Thus, we believe that we have confirmed the model (Martins, 2012) that evidences school occupation as a category.

Although this study was not a direct fieldwork, practical experience is present in most statements. The research that gave basis to the theoretical debate proposed here, for the most part, was carried out directly with experiences of school occupations, whose strategy of information collection took place in dialogue with the subjects of the occupations themselves. That is, it is a theorized result, but immersed in praxis in motion.

Occupying schools is a process of full use, on the part of the subjects concerned, of the school apparatus. Any occupation is made from political debates, which, in a Democratic State, presupposes community participation in school daily life, hence the political dimension of the occupation comes. Schools are the spaces for sharing knowledge, but it is not a horizontal relationship, in which science is dogmatic. The set of traditional knowledge, collective and cultural identities, learn, but also teach, as a presupposition of the sociocultural dimension. This process is performed collectively. The experiences and collective actions generate learning and constitute collective subjects, armed with expanded skills and plurals of knowledge, it is the premise contained in the collective dimension of the school occupations. Finally, the synthesis of the processes described, and the own dynamics of school occupations, leads to an appropriation of the subjects involved, of the knowledge set originating from praxis, which culminates in learning, which highlights the pedagogical dimension of school occupations.

Evidencing the educational potential of each of the dimensions, and locating in the practices already studied, which take place within educational actions, centered on school situations, it was possible to affirm that the exercise of school occupations, by students, the school community and external community, constitute, by the learning generated, a pedagogy. And as already evidenced, it is a pedagogy that envisions a process of transforming praxis. The cases analyzed showed that the occupation process is strengthened among many pedagogical dimensions, the teaching-learning of those involved. Thus, we understand the need to optimize school occupations as a strategy of transformation and learning.

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